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Morphological Differences between Japanese and Korean: A Comparative Study

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***Abstract:** This study aims to compare the morphological structures of the Japanese and Korean languages. Taking into account the historical context, where the country was under Japanese colonial influence, the research analysed how the Japanese language affected the linguistic system of Korea as a result of prolonged cultural interaction. The study is based on comparative lexicography, analysing changes in word meanings and their adaptation in both languages. The comparative analysis method is applied to the morphological categories of the Japanese and Korean languages, particularly focusing on how parts of speech (nouns, verbs, adjectives) are expressed and analysing morphemic structures and their variations. The study draws on a wide range of lexical and grammatical resources to precisely analyse morphological phenomena.*

The study results reveal that loanwords in both languages often undergo shifts in meaning, sometimes acquiring a negative connotation in Korean. It was found that in Korean, Japanese words undergo phonological transformations and changes

in their morphological structure during the adaptation process. The most significant changes are in meaning, especially in Korean, where positive Japanese words take on a negative nuance. The study also identified several significant morphological differences between Japanese and Korean. While both languages have an agglutinative structure, the means of expressing grammatical categories differ considerably. Japanese employs more synthetic forms, whereas Korean has a more varied approach to forming noun and verb forms through suffix addition and root modification. Differences were also observed in the expression of numerals, tense, and modality, where Koreans use specific ways of forming case and tense categories. In conclusion, the results demonstrate that despite their shared historical heritage and the influence of Japanese, Koreans show different ways of adapting Japanese loanwords. This underscores the importance of each language's cultural context and linguistic peculiarities when interpreting foreign linguistic elements.

Keywords: *phonological changes, semantic changes, morphology, language contact, agglutinative languages, loanwords.*

Introduction. The morphological differences between Japanese and Korean are an important aspect of research regarding language contact influences that arise from historical, cultural and social changes. These languages have an agglutinative structure, but their morphology differs significantly in how they express grammatical categories such as gender, number, case, tense, aspect, and modality. This poses a challenge for researchers to analyse the similarities and differences between these languages in more depth and to find out how Japanese, being a contact language, has influenced the Korean morphological system.

The relevance of this study is due to several factors. Firstly, although language contact between Japan and Korea has been ongoing for over a century, the issues of morphological changes and adaptations remain insufficiently studied in comparative research. Most existing studies focus on lexical borrowings without paying sufficient attention to the morphological processes that accompany these borrowings. This

study proposes a new approach focusing on the morphological changes due to long-term interaction between two languages.

Secondly, studying morphological differences is important for comparative linguistics, as it allows us to determine which linguistic mechanisms lead to changes in the language system due to cultural and social influences. Studying this phenomenon is also important for understanding linguistic assimilation and adaptation processes, which are particularly relevant in the context of globalisation and international contacts.

Currently, there is a significant theoretical gap in the study of Japanese influence on Korean morphology. In particular, there are questions about the nature and extent of phonological and morphological transformations of Japanese loanwords in Korean, as well as different approaches to loanword adaptation, particularly in the context of Korean agglutinative morphology. This knowledge gap may be important for developing new theoretical language contact and adaptation models within agglutinative languages. Thus, this topic is not only theoretically significant but also practically important in the context of modern language contact. Understanding how the morphological structure of borrowings changes in two different agglutinative languages makes it possible to contribute to the development of modern comparative linguistics research and help solve applied problems related to the study of a language through the prism of its interaction with other cultures and languages. This study will also contribute to expanding our understanding of morphological processes in languages that have a similar structural base but different ways of development through language contact. The results can be useful for linguists working on the theory of language contact, as well as for lexicographers and dialectologists studying the influence of other languages on the Korean language system. Thus, the present study reveals important aspects of language interaction that enrich understanding language structure and adaptation in language contact.

Literature review. Previous studies of Japanese borrowings in other languages, including Korean, have mostly focused on a separate analysis of each language without comparing these processes [12, p. 413]. In particular, in scientific

works on the Korean language, there is a systematisation of Japanese borrowings, which allows for a better understanding of their impact on the language structure [13]. One of these studies classifies Japanese borrowings in Korean into three main categories: Japanese words proper, Japanese Chinese words, and Japanese borrowings from other foreign languages [15]. At the same time, an analysis of changes in the use of these words in different historical periods was carried out, which made it possible to assess how the cultural and political context affects language changes [11]. In addition, related studies have shown that in the Korean language, Japanese borrowings have undergone significant phonetic changes, which indicates the specifics of adapting external vocabulary to the internal language system [10, p. 301].

In particular, the study of phonetic and semantic changes in the Korean language included the frequency of Japanese borrowings among different generations [14]. Such studies have made it possible to divide borrowings into several categories, such as borrowings from Japanese through Western languages, Japanese Chinese words, combinations of Japanese and Korean words, and translated borrowings [3]. Semantic changes in the meaning of words have also been an important aspect of this analysis, with some Japanese words being noted to have acquired negative connotations in the Korean context [1]. This indicates the influence of social and cultural factors that change the perception of borrowings in the adaptation process. As for the Korean language, studying Japanese borrowings in this context provides an even more comprehensive picture. Japanese borrowings in Korean were classified into three categories in one of the works: purely phonetic, partially phonetic and Chinese forms of borrowings [2, p. 17]. In addition, 10 subcategories were identified that consider phonetic and semantic features of borrowings that changed their meaning over time depending on the linguistic context [6]. Other studies indicate a more detailed classification, dividing borrowings into four main categories depending on how accurately they reproduce Japanese pronunciation, preserve Japanese characters, or acquire local pronunciation and writing of the Korean language [4, p. 45]. One of the important parts of the study is

to determine the frequency of borrowings using surveys that allow us to assess the popularity of Japanese words among different age and social groups.

The peculiarity of Korean language research is the emphasis on the age and geographical aspects of borrowing. Some researchers have analysed the frequency of use of 60 Japanese borrowings, classifying them by age groups and regions of Taiwan (north, centre, south). This made it possible to assess not only the lexical influence of the Japanese language but also the socio-cultural factors that determine the popularity of certain words [5].

A comparative analysis of Japanese loanwords in Korean also highlights different approaches to classification depending on the criteria used to study language contact. Some studies divide Japanese borrowings into categories based on form, phonology, and semantics, while other approaches focus on the variability of word meanings and their adaptation to new social and cultural conditions [7, p. 183]. One important area is the study of phonological changes, which allow us to identify the specifics of the adaptation of foreign words to the sound system of each language.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the general problem.

Despite the significant achievements in studying Japanese borrowings in Korean, several aspects remain insufficiently researched and require further study. The first is the lack of integration of a comparative approach to studying Japanese borrowings in different languages, including Korean. Previous studies focus on borrowings in each language separately, which limits the possibility of identifying common patterns and differences in adapting Japanese words in different linguistic contexts. This issue requires further analysis to understand the general principles of language contact and the influence of Japanese on agglutinative language systems.

The second important aspect is the insufficient in-depth study of phonological and morphological changes in Japanese borrowings. Most previous studies focus on lexical or semantic aspects, but the study of changes in word structure, particularly their morphological adaptation to Korean, remains limited.

To date, there is a limited empirical base for studying the influence of age and social and regional factors on the use of Japanese loanwords in Korean. Most studies

cover a limited number of words or groups of speakers, which makes it impossible to fully assess general trends in loanword use across generations and geographical regions. Estimating the frequency of loanword use based on broader and more representative samples could provide a much deeper understanding of linguistic dynamics and the impact of sociocultural changes on language practice.

These knowledge gaps are important for further developing the theory of language contact and language adaptation. Solving these problems will allow us to deepen our understanding of the mechanisms of adaptation of borrowings in two different languages and identify the principles of their phonological and morphological transformations, which opens up new opportunities for studying language influence in agglutinative languages.

The present study aims to fill these gaps, particularly by comparing Japanese loanwords in Korean with a focus on morphological and phonological changes. Expanding the empirical base, including new methodological approaches, and a detailed analysis of different age, social and regional groups will allow for a more comprehensive assessment of language adaptation processes. Thus, the results of this study will contribute to developing the theory of language contact and help expand our understanding of how foreign borrowings are adapted in different languages depending on their structural and sociocultural features.

Formulation of the article's objectives (statement of the task)

This article aims to conduct a comparative study of morphological differences between Japanese and Korean, with a special focus on the analysis of Japanese borrowings. The main task is to identify and analyse the key morphological, phonological, and semantic transformations that occur with Japanese loanwords during their adaptation to the Korean grammatical system.

The primary task is to classify Japanese borrowings in Korean by morphological form, phonological changes and changes in meaning. An important aspect of the study is a comparative analysis of the morphological features of borrowings in Japanese and Korean, particularly the adaptation mechanisms of parts of speech such as nouns, verbs and adjectives.

The study also covers the analysis of phonological changes in Japanese loanwords in Korean, including changes in sounds and pronunciation and their impact on grammatical categories. As part of this analysis, attention is paid to the specific mechanisms of phonetic adaptation that ensure the integration of foreign words into the Korean language system. Another task is to study semantic changes in Japanese borrowings, particularly word meanings in different linguistic contexts, and their impact on socio-cultural and linguistic relations between Japan and Korea. This aspect of the study reveals how the cultural peculiarities of both languages influence the adaptation and formation of new linguistic units. The work aims to deepen the understanding of how language systems, particularly agglutinative languages, adapt foreign borrowings. At the same time, it is important to identify general and specific trends that arise due to long-term linguistic contact between Japanese and Korean cultures.

Results. Morphological differences between Japanese and Korean are an important aspect for comparative studies. Both languages have unique characteristics that determine their phonological structure. Japanese contains 5 simple vowels that can vary in pitch, which is also important for changing lexical meaning. The Korean language, in turn, also has a system of vowels and consonants, but the classification of vowels and their use in language practice are somewhat different [8]. A comparison of vowel classifications by type of articulation allows us to better understand the linguistic features of each language. Japanese has 5 simple vowels, which are written with hiragana as あ, い, う, え, お. Vowels in Japanese can be classified according to such criteria as the front or back of the tongue, tongue height, and the presence of lip rounding. The classification looks like this (Table 1):

Table 1

Criteria for vowel classification in Japanese

Criterion	Characteristics
Front or back of the tongue	Front vowels: い (i), え (e), which are pronounced with the tongue raised to the front of the mouth.

	Back vowels: あ (a), う (u), お (o), which are formed by lifting the tongue to the back of the mouth.
Tongue height	High vowels: い (i), う (u), where the tongue is raised high to the sky. Mid vowels: え (e), お (o), where the tongue is at a medium height. Low vowels: あ (a), where the tongue is lowered low in the mouth.
The presence of lip rounding	Unrounded vowels: い (i), え (e), which are pronounced without rounding the lips. Rounded vowels: う (u), お (o), where the lips are rounded when pronounced.

Source: [10].

This classification allows you to systematise the vowels of the Japanese language according to their physiological articulation and clearly distinguish between them. It is important for a proper understanding of the phonological structure of Japanese and for analysing its phonetic differences from other languages, such as Korean.

Korea's vowel system is also a basis for comparison, as it has similarities and important differences in vowel classification. Therefore, a comparative analysis of these vowel systems can contribute to a better understanding of the specifics of each language (Table 2):

Table 2

Comparative analysis of the vowel systems of Japanese and Korean

Vowel type	Japanese (example)	Pronunciation of Japanese vowels	Korean (example)
High	ㅣ (i), ㅡ (u) /i/	ㅣ (i), ㅜ (u)	(closed) /i/, /u/
High (closed)	ㅣ (i)	ㅜ (u) /i/, /u/	ㅣ (i), ㅡ (u)/
Medium (semi-open)	ㅐ (e), ㅓ (o)	/e/, /o/	ㅐ (e), ㅓ (o)
Low (open)	ㅏ (a)	/a/	ㅏ (a)

Source: [9].

Despite their common history and cultural exchange, Japanese and Korean show significant morphological differences, especially in the formation and use of loanwords. This study focuses on four main types of loanwords: Japanese proper words, Chinese loanwords, foreign loanwords, and hybrid words.

Borrowing Japanese proper words in Korean is often based on using Chinese characters with kun-reading or combined writing that includes katakana. In the case of everyday vocabulary, such borrowings often retain Japanese phonetics. However, Chinese borrowings from Japanese are usually adapted through Chinese character readings, typical for technical and specialised terms, particularly in work or educational environments.

Hybrid words that combine elements of Chinese and Japanese origin show different implementation forms. Even if the Japanese spelling is retained in Korean, pronunciation is often adapted to local norms. The borrowing of foreign words through Japanese, such as terms of English or Portuguese origin, is adapted according to the phonetic principle but retains the structural features of Japanese.

As for the implementation of borrowings in Korean, it is noted that this language preserves Japanese phonetics to a lesser extent, especially for Chinese borrowings. The vocabulary that retains Japanese sounds is mostly related to everyday concepts, such as names of people, plants, or body parts. In technical fields, however, adapted words with Chinese readings prevail.

The borrowings from Japanese to Korean demonstrate a complex relationship between phonetic adaptation, morphological structure, and sphere of use. The differences in the borrowing approach reflect historical and cultural interactions and the internal linguistic features of each language.

It should be noted that Korean and Japanese, despite their historical influence on each other, demonstrate unique linguistic features that affect the forms of borrowing. The Korean language actively integrates Japanese borrowings, combining them with its linguistic elements to create unique lexical constructions. This allows for a more detailed or contextually adapted meaning better suited to cultural and linguistic norms.

One of the key features of the Korean language is its ability to organically adapt borrowings by combining them with local components. For example, words of Japanese origin are often integrated into Korean compound structures that include local suffixes, prefixes, or roots. Such a combination reinforces the word's meaning when adding a Korean component to a Japanese loanword indicates a more specific context or emotional connotation. It also clarifies the meaning, as local elements can act as explanatory particles that make the word more understandable to native speakers. In addition, adaptation allows for creating new lexemes, i.e. terms that have no direct analogues in Japanese or other languages.

An example of such an adaptation is using Japanese technical terms in Korean, which receive local adaptations in the context of science or technology. Such adaptations often involve the addition of Korean suffixes to form nouns, adjectives, or verbs, which extends the functionality of the loanwords in the language.

In terms of phonetic and semantic adaptations, Korean shows marked phonetic changes during the integration of loanwords. For example, Japanese words that contain complex syllables may be simplified to facilitate pronunciation. In addition, some sounds that are difficult for Korean speakers to reproduce are replaced with sounds that better match their phonetic system.

Semantic adaptations also play an important role in the borrowing process. The meaning of Japanese words in Korean can change depending on the context. In some cases, it expands the word's original meaning, while in others, it narrows it down to suit the usage in a particular industry. For example, technical terms may take on new meanings in fields such as medicine, education, or industry to accommodate the specific needs of those industries.

Cultural context also plays a key role in shaping borrowing. For example, borrowings related to everyday life, such as food, clothing, or social interactions, are often adapted with minimal changes because their meaning is understood in both cultures. In technical or formal areas, adaptation is more complex and may involve the creation of new terms.

Unlike Koreans, the Japanese retain greater structural stability when borrowing. For example, words of English or Chinese origin are often integrated into Japanese without significant phonetic or morphological modification. Instead, Koreans actively transform borrowings, adapting them to fit their internal norms.

Adapting Japanese borrowings in Korean reflects a complex process of language transformation, including phonetic, morphological and semantic adaptation. Combining borrowings with local elements creates a unique lexical base that meets linguistic and cultural needs. This process illustrates the deep connection between language and society, emphasising the dynamic nature of language development in intercultural interaction.

Conclusions. The morphological differences between Japanese and Korean are an essential aspect of comparative linguistic analysis, as they reflect historical relationships and each language's internal dynamics. Japanese, characterised by a stable phonological system with five vowels, demonstrates structural consistency in the borrowing process. Its vocabulary largely retains its phonetic and morphological structure even when integrating English, Chinese or other borrowings.

On the other hand, Korean is characterised by actively adapting loanwords, especially from Japanese, and integrating them with local linguistic elements. This creates unique lexical constructions that align with cultural and linguistic norms. The adaptation process includes essential aspects such as phonetic adaptations, morphological changes, and semantic modifications, which allow borrowings to fit seamlessly into the Korean language system.

The cultural context plays a vital role in the adaptation process. In the Korean language, borrowings from Japanese demonstrate flexibility in use. Everyday vocabulary mainly retains Japanese phonetics, while technical vocabulary is often adapted through Chinese character readings. This contributes to enriching the Korean language and creating hybrid terms that have unique meanings for both languages.

A comparative analysis of the phonological systems of vowels in Japanese and Korean shows significant differences in classification and articulation. The Japanese

vowel system is more stable, while the Korean system has a more complex articulatory organisation, which adds depth to the process of studying language interaction.

Thus, the comparative study of Japanese and Korean illustrates the complex language interaction and transformation process. The analysis's results are valuable not only for linguistic research but also for understanding the cultural specifics of both languages. The study of such differences contributes to a better understanding of the dynamics of language development and the integration of lexical borrowings in the context of intercultural interaction.

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